

MORNING HABITS and BODY WEIGHT: THE ROLE of BREAKFAST in an ALGERIAN ADULT POPULATION

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Abstract— Objectives: To describe breakfast habits and examine their relationship with weight status.

Materials and methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 1000 Algerian adults. Data were collected using a questionnaire that asked about dietary habits related to breakfast. Daily food consumption was estimated using a 24-hour recall repeated three times. Anthropometric measurements consisted of weight and height. Breakfast intake was assessed based on breakfast energy intake (15% of daily energy intake).

Results: Our population includes 60.2% women. A total of 55.3% of participants are overweight, including obesity. Breakfast consumers represent 51.6% of the subjects. Breakfast is consumed at home by the majority of the population, in less than 15 minutes on average. More than half of the individuals eat it alone, without engaging in any activity. The breakfast consumed by our subjects is an important source of carbohydrates, fats, and calcium. No significant difference was found in the prevalence of overweight and obesity between breakfast consumers and skippers. No correlation was found between breakfast energy intake and BMI. Breakfast consumers show a better nutritional profile compared to breakfast skippers.

Conclusion: Our study shows that eating breakfast is not associated with body weight.

Keywords— Breakfast, BMI, obesity, adults, energy intake

I. INTRODUCTION

The diets of societies have evolved over time in response to changing lifestyles [1]. Societies tend to converge towards diets rich in fats, sugar and refined foods, and low in fiber, as well as sedentary lifestyles [2], which leads to the emergence of overweight and obesity. Overweight and obesity are major public health problems worldwide that are increasing at an alarming rate. In 2016, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that 1.9 billion adults worldwide were overweight, of whom 650 million were obese [3]. In Algeria, the latest statistics from 2016 indicate that the overall prevalence of overweight and obesity is 55.6% (48.3% in men and 63.3% in women) [4]. Obesity is a multifactorial disease due to urbanization, a sedentary lifestyle, an accelerated pace of life, shifting work schedules and the dominant influence of the food industry and advertising [5]. Eating habits also play a significant role in the development of obesity [6]. Observational studies have revealed a link between obesity and a low frequency of meals [7,8]. Furthermore, how meals are distributed over the 24-hour period may also be a contributor. Of the three main meals, breakfast has been the subject of a large number of studies investigating its association with body weight [9].

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Between October 2021 and April 2023, a cross-sectional study of 1,000 Algerian adults was carried out. Participants were selected using the all-comers method from various locations, including factories, schools, stores, and households.

Data were collected using a questionnaire that described breakfast related eating habits and was completed via face-to-face interviews with the subjects. The collected data concerned the place of consumption (home or out of home) conviviality during consumption (alone or accompanied) and the duration of consumption (less than 5 minutes, 5 to 10 minutes, 10 to 15 minutes or more than 15 minutes).

It also covered the behavior of the subjects during consumption (screen usage, conversation or other activities). Daily food intake was assessed using a 24-hour recall repeated three times.

Breakfast consumption is defined according to the energy intake from this meal, which should represent 15-20% of the total recommended energy intake for adults (2.000-2.500 kcal) [10,11]. The lower limit of this range was adopted to assess breakfast energy intake, equivalent to 300 kcal. Participants were categorized as either «breakfast consumers» those with an energy intake of at least 300 kcal or «breakfast skippers» those with an energy intake of less than 300 kcal [12].

Anthropometric measurements were taken according to the techniques recommended by the World Health Organization [13]. The weight and height of each subject were measured to assess their weight status, and their body mass index (BMI) was calculated. Weight was measured using a SECA mechanical scale with a 150 kg capacity. Height was measured in a standing position without shoes using a SECA measuring tape with 1 mm precision.

The data were analyzed using SPSS version 26 software. Quantitative variables were presented as the mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and qualitative variables as percentages. Student's t-test for independent samples was used to compare continuous variables. The chi squared test was used to compare qualitative variables. The Pearson correlation test was used to analyze correlations between the variables. The significance level was fixed at 0.05.

III.RESULT

A. Population description

The general characteristics of the survey population were presented in Table 1. BMI values ranged from 18,5 kg/m² to 45.7 kg/m², with an average of 26.3 \pm 4.8 kg/m². Women had significantly higher BMI values (27.1 \pm 5.1 kg/m² vs 25.2 \pm 4.2 kg/m²; p = 0.000). In terms of weight status, 55.3% of subjects were overweight including obese (OOB), with a female predominance (61.5% vs 46%; p=0.000). Among the participants, 51.6% consumed breakfast, of whom 54.4% were women. Among those who skipped breakfast, women were more likely did it (65.9% vs 34.1%, p =0.000). According to weight status, the prevalence of OOB was found to be 56.4% among consumers and 55,2% among skippers, with no significant difference (p = 0.71) (Fig1). Three reasons were cited by most of our subjects for eating breakfast: it was an important meal (31%), it was a habit (28.3%), and they felt hungry (30.1%). Among breakfast skippers, 31.8% did not eat breakfast due to morning nausea, 24.1% due to lack of time and 21.2% due to waking up late.

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS of STUDY POPULATION (MEAN \pm SD)

	Total
Age (years)	33.9 \pm 10.1
Weight (Kg)	74.3 \pm 13.9
Height (m)	1.68 \pm 0.89
BMI (Kg/m ²)	26.3 \pm 4.8
Men/ Women (%)	39.8%/ 60.2%
Weight status (%)	
Normal weight	44.7%
OOB	55.3%

BMI: Body Mass Index. OOB: Overweight and Obese Individuals.

Fig1. Distribution of breakfast consumers and skippers by sex and weight status.

OOB: Overweight and obese individuals.

B. Breakfast environment

The majority of consumers (87.7%) ate breakfast at home, with a predominance of OOB ($p=0.003$). More men ate breakfast outside the home (22.3% vs 3.9%; $p=0.000$). Half of consumers ate breakfast alone, with more men than women doing so ($p=0.01$). No significant differences were found according to weight status (Table 2). Over three-quarters of the subjects ate breakfast in less than 15 minutes, with half of them eating it in between 5 to 10 minutes. Men were more likely to eat breakfast within 5 to 10 min ($p=0.03$), while women were more numerous to eat breakfast within 10 to 15 min ($p=0.005$). No significant differences were observed according to weight status. During breakfast, more than half of the subjects (57.8%) consumed it without any other activity, while 21.6% discussed it, with a female majority ($p=0.03$).

TABLE II. BREAKFAST CONSUMPTION ENVIRONNEMENT by GENDER and WEIGHT

	Total	Women	Men	Normal weight	OOB
Breakfast duration (%)					
Under 5 minutes	17.4	14.6	22.4	16.9	22.1
5 to 10 minutes	49.9	45.3	59.7*	51.2	48.8
10 to 15 minutes	22.6	27.6*	17.9	23.2	17.8
More than 15 minutes	10.1	12.6	7.7	8.7	11.2
Breakfast behavior (%)					
Nothing	57.8	58	60.2	53.1	61.6
Screen usage	20.6	16.7	16.1	22.7	19
Conversation	21.6	25.3*	23.7	24.2	19.4
Conviviality (%)					
Alone	50.8	43.7	59.2*	52.2	49.6
Place (%)					
Home	87.7	96.1*	77.7	84.1	90.7**

* Significant Difference Between Women and Men, $p < 0.05$. ** Significant Difference Between Normal Weight and OOBs, $p < 0.05$. OOB: Overweight and Obese Individuals.

C. Breakfast energy and nutritional intake

Breakfast energy and nutrient intake for all consumers and by sex was shown in Table III. The average energy intake at breakfast was 442.9 ± 141.1 kcal. Men consumed more energy than women ($p = 0.02$). No correlation was found between breakfast energy intake and BMI. In terms of nutrients, men consumed more carbohydrates, fiber and calcium at breakfast than women did ($p=0.02$, $p=0.03$ and $p=0.01$, respectively). The contribution of breakfast to total daily energy and nutrient intake was shown in Fig 2. In our population, breakfast contributed $23.8 \pm 7.4\%$ to total energy intake. In terms of macronutrients, protein contributed to $18.9 \pm 7.3\%$ of daily macronutrient intake, carbohydrates to $24.3 \pm 8.9\%$, and lipids to $25.3 \pm 12.6\%$. Breakfast consumed among our population showed a significant contribution, exceeding 20% of the total intake of cholesterol, Saturated Fatty Acids (SFA) and Monounsaturated Fatty Acids (MUFA), vitamins A and D, and the minerals calcium, phosphorus and magnesium.

TABLE III. ENERGY and NUTRITIONAL INTAKE of BREAKFAST by SEX.

	Total	Women	Men
Energy (Kcal)	442.9 ± 141.1	424.1 ± 120	465.2 ± 160 *
Carbohydrates (g)	65.6 ± 26.9	62.2 ± 24.9	69.8 ± 28.7 *
Fiber (g)	2 ± 2.1	1.8 ± 1.4	2.2 ± 2.5 *
Protein (g)	12.9 ± 4.6	12.9 ± 3.9	12.9 ± 5.3
Fat (g)	13.8 ± 8.7	13.4 ± 7.7	14.3 ± 9.8
SFA (g)	7.9 ± 5.1	7.7 ± 4.4	8.2 ± 5.7
MUFA (g)	4.5 ± 3.4	4.2 ± 3.2	4.8 ± 3.6
PUFA (g)	1 ± 1.1	1 ± 0.9	1.1 ± 1.2
Cholesterol (mg)	40.2 ± 50.9	39.5 ± 42.6	41 ± 59.4
Vitamin A (µg)	76.1 ± 57.1	78.6 ± 48.9	73.1 ± 65.5
Vitamin D (µg)	0.2 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.3	0.2 ± 0.4
Calcium (mg)	253.4 ± 105.8	267.8 ± 109.1*	236.3 ± 99.3
Magnesium (mg)	41.7 ± 22.2	40.3 ± 15.8	43.3 ± 28
Phosphorus (mg)	239.1 ± 96.5	240.6 ± 81.7	237.2 ± 111.9
Iron (mg)	1.4 ± 1.6	1.4 ± 1.6	1.5 ± 1.6

* Significant Difference Between Women and Men, $p < 0.05$. SFA: Saturated Fatty Acids. MUFA: Monounsaturated Fatty Acids. PUFA: Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids.

Fig 2. Breakfast's contribution to daily energy and nutritional intake.

D. Nutritional profiles of breakfast consumers and skippers

Table 4 showed the nutritional profiles of breakfast consumers and skippers. The average daily energy intake of breakfast consumers was 1930.6 ± 530.7 kcal, which was higher than that of skippers ($p = 0.000$). Breakfast consumers had higher daily intakes of macronutrients, vitamins, and minerals, except for iron and fiber. When breakfast intake was excluded from the analysis (Table 4), there were no significant differences between breakfast consumers and skippers for macronutrients, vitamins, and minerals, except for fiber intake ($p = 0.193$) and iron intake ($p = 0.663$).

TABLE IV. DAILY ENERGY and NUTRIENT INTAKE, EXCLUDING BREAKFAST for CONSUMERS AND BREAKFAST SKIPPERS.

	Daily energy and nutrient intakes		Daily energy and nutrient intakes excluding breakfast	
	Consumers	Skippers	Consumers	Skippers
Energy (Kcal)	1930.6 ± 530.7*	1626.9 ± 386.4	1487.7 ± 492.8	1467.3 ± 374
Carbohydrates (g)	274.7 ± 87.9*	221.1 ± 62.9	59.4 ± 21.9	57.9 ± 18.4
Fiber (g)	17.9 ± 8.6	17.2 ± 8.8	208.9 ± 78.6*	197.9 ± 61.4
Protein (g)	72.3 ± 23.1*	63.2 ± 18.5	42.8 ± 22.2	41.6 ± 19.5
Fat (g)	56.6 ± 25.5*	46.7 ± 20.9	15.9 ± 8.3	16.5 ± 8.8
SFA (g)	27.2 ± 12.6 *	14.5 ± 8.1	149.4 ± 116.6	142.8 ± 102.5
MUFA (g)	19.2 ± 9.6 *	12.6 ± 7.6	19.3 ± 10.9	20 ± 10.2
PUFA (g)	8.7 ± 4.9 *	7.5 ± 4.2	14.7 ± 8.6	14.6 ± 7.7
Cholesterol (mg)	190 ± 132.5*	159.6 ± 106.9	7.7 ± 4.9	7.2 ± 4.1
Vitamin A (µg)	195.5 ± 132.2*	152.4 ± 170.9	119.4 ± 115.9	119.2 ± 164.8
Vitamin D (µg)	1.2 ± 1.8*	0.9 ± 1.4	1.0 ± 1.8	0.9 ± 1.4
Calcium (mg)	586.9 ± 232.8*	456.1 ± 229.2	332.9 ± 181.9	322.6 ± 166.9
Magnesium (mg)	212.2 ± 71.1*	183.7 ± 60.4	170.6 ± 63.9	165.3 ± 59.4
Phosphorus (mg)	1000.5 ± 341.5 *	891.2 ± 319.7	761.4 ± 301.9*	705.4 ± 280.5
Iron (mg)	11.5 ± 9.5	11.2 ± 8.1	10.1 ± 8.4	10.6 ± 7.7

*Significant Difference Between Breakfast Consumers and Breakfast Skippers, $p < 0.05$. SFA: Saturated Fatty Acids. MUFA: Monounsaturated Fatty Acids.

PUFA: Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids.

IV. DISCUSSION

In the present study, consumption or not of breakfast defined by the energy intake of the meal. The energy provided by breakfast is important because it directly affects our energy levels, mental performance, eating habits, and therefore our overall health.

In this population, 51.6% of subjects consumed breakfast. There was no significant difference in the prevalence of OOB between breakfast consumers and skippers. There was also no correlation between breakfast energy intake and BMI. A large number of cross-sectional studies, cohort studies, randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses investigate the relationship between skipping breakfast and adult obesity and overweight. However, the results are contradictory. Our results accorded with those of some studies that find no association between skipping breakfast and BMI [14,15]. However, other studies support the hypothesis that skipping breakfast is associated with obesity [16,17,18]. While Dashti *et al.* [19] establish a causal link between skipping breakfast and obesity, randomized controlled trials reveal

more mixed findings [20,21]. In 2019, a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials on adults shows a small weight difference (0.44kg) in favor of breakfast skippers [22].

The reasons given by our subjects for eating or skipping breakfast included the importance of the meal, habit, feeling hungry, morning nausea, lack of time, and waking up late. These reasons are similar to those found in the literature. In Reeves *et al.* [23] study, subjects report eating breakfast to have energy (70.2%), to avoid feeling hungry before breakfast (73.9%), as a habit (57.4%), and to lose weight (23.5%). Other studies report lack of time, waking up late, not feeling hungry, lack of appetite, concerns about weight, and pathological issues such as nausea, diarrhea, and vomiting as reasons for skipping breakfast [24,25]. Breakfast has long been considered the most important meal of the day [26], because it provides the sustenance and energy required for daily activities [27]. Furthermore, several studies confirm that it contributes to better nutritional profiles and a healthier lifestyle [28,11]. Eating breakfast is a part of the morning routine for many people. This is influenced by tradition, culture, and family habits. In the study by Rai *et al.* [29], all of the participants believe that breakfast is an important meal because they feel in a good mood, are more active and are able to concentrate better after eating it.

A. Breakfast environment

Although a meal corresponds to a biological function, it is also a social event. Where and with whom we eat are important social factors [30]. Our study showed that over three-quarters of consumers ate breakfast at home in less than 15 minutes, with half of them eating alone. Our results were consistent with those reported by Chikhi & Padilla [31] for an Algerian adult population. They find that 81.4% of participants prefer to eat breakfast at home and that 87% of participants take less than 15 minutes to eat. The time taken to eat breakfast tends to be more limited than for other meals, as it is influenced by the time of waking up and the first household and work-related activities of the morning. Among Spanish adults, the average time spent eating breakfast is between 9 and 11 minutes [32].

In our population, men were the quickest to eat breakfast and the most numerous to eat it alone and away from home. Those who were OOB were the most likely to eat breakfast at home. Fast eaters may be solitary eaters; they eat quickly to minimize the social anxiety associated with eating. Also, the duration of a meal increases with the number of people present [33]. According to Giovannini *et al.* [34], the ideal breakfast should be eaten together as a family, with parents setting a good example for their children.

More than half of our subjects ate breakfast without any other activity, while a quarter ate it in front of a screen or in conversation. Eating behaviors depend on individual preferences; some people prefer to eat breakfast in front of a screen or while browsing social networks, as it is a quick way to access information in the morning. According to a study by Bellisle *et al.* [35], most French people do nothing during breakfast time, while 30% eat breakfast in front of a screen.

B. Breakfast energy and nutritional intake

Breakfast energy intake averaged at 442.9 ± 141.1 kcal, which is equivalent to $23.8 \pm 7.4\%$ of total energy intake. According to O'Neil *et al.* [11], breakfast should represent 15-25% of daily energy intake, corresponding to 300-500 kcal for women and 375-625 kcal for men [27]. However, a wide divergence in the energy consumed at breakfast has been observed in the literature. In France, the average energy intake from breakfast for adults is 325.1 ± 200.1 kcal (16.7%) [35]. In Ireland, the average energy intake at breakfast is 400 ± 193 kcal (19.9%) [36]. The ELANS study in Latin America indicates that breakfast caloric intake is 444 kcal (23%) [37]. In Spain, the average breakfast consumed by adults provides 293 kcal (18%) [32].

In terms of nutrient intake, our subjects consumed an average of 65.6 ± 26.9 g of carbohydrates, 2 ± 2.1 g of fiber, 12.9 ± 4.6 g of protein, and 13.8 ± 8.7 g of lipids. There was considerable variation in macronutrient intake between studies. When compared to populations from the Mediterranean region, the fiber, lipid and protein intakes of our subjects are similar to those reported by Ruiz *et al.* [32]; however, their breakfasts provide fewer carbohydrates (37.9 g). A French breakfast provides more fiber (2.4 ± 2 g)

than that of our population but less lipids (9.9 ± 7.7 g) and protein (8.9 ± 6.6 g) [35]. Other studies indicate that breakfasts consumed by adults in the United Kingdom (3 g) and Denmark (5 g) are rich in fiber [38,39]. The vitamin A and D intake of our population was very low compared to the values reported by Fagt *et al.* [38] (155 ± 244 μ g and 0.4 ± 0.5 μ g, respectively) and Gaal *et al.* [39] (102 ± 228 μ g and 2.2 ± 1.4 μ g, respectively). However, vitamin A intake is similar to that reported for the French population (75.3 ± 84.6 μ g) [35].

Nutrient intake in a quality breakfast should meet at a minimum 10% of daily nutrient intake; with a target of 20% or more [11]. Our population's breakfast exceeded the 10% minimum for all nutrients analyzed. It was rich in carbohydrates, lipids, SFAs, MUFAs, vitamins A and D, calcium, phosphorus and magnesium; the percentage contribution of these nutrients to daily nutrient intake met or exceeded the recommended 20%. Our results regarding carbohydrate, protein and lipid contribution were comparable to those found by Bellisle *et al.* and Fisberg *et al.* [35,37].

C. Nutritional profiles of breakfast consumers and skippers

Breakfast consumers had a superior nutritional profile compared to skippers, with higher daily energy and macronutrient intake, vitamins and minerals. Our results showed that the energy and nutrients not consumed by skipping breakfast were not compensated for in subsequent meals. The data collected in our study was consistent with the findings of Sievert *et al.* [22] who observe an average difference of 259.79 kcal higher among breakfast consumers. When we compared daily energy and nutrient intakes excluding breakfast, we found no difference between breakfast consumers and skippers. This suggests that no dietary compensation occurs during the day. This could partly explain why skipping breakfast has no effect on body weight. Furthermore, several studies demonstrate that skipping breakfast does not lead to subsequent energy compensation [40,22]. Further, these authors propose that skipping breakfast could effectively reduce total energy intake.

V. CONCLUSION

This study examines the nutritional benefits of breakfast and its contribution to daily nutritional intake in a population of Algerian adults. The breakfast consumed by our population contributes significantly to total energy intake. Despite being rich in carbohydrates and fats, it also provides significant amounts of vitamins and minerals. These nutritional contributions would not be compensated by later meals, if breakfast is skipped. Our results could contribute to the development of nutritional recommendations for a balanced breakfast. The result of our study found no relationship between breakfast consumption and body weight. Of course, we are not opposed to breakfast, which offers benefits for most consumers of all ages; however, it should not be promoted as an absolute requirement for everyone in the hope of reducing obesity.

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